

APPLICATIONS OF FRP COMPOSITES ON BEND AND COMPLICATED SHAPE STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY

The FRP show a remarkable effect when the long continuous fibers are placed along with the stress flow especially at the stress concentration points. In this paper we developed new moulding process, in which we perform the fiber cutting just after continuous fiber placement process and just at the low stress area. By this process we can place the continuous fibers along with the stress flow especially at the stress concentration points. Then we developed new FRP specimens to obtain the strength criterion considering both of fiber failure and delamination.

Keywords: FRP, Moulding, Strength, Long fiber, Short fiber, Bend Shape, Complicated shape

MOULDING AND STRENGTH PROBLEMS ON THE AAPPLICATIONS OF FRP COMPOSITES ON BEND AND COMPLICATED SHAPE PARTS

FRP composites are attractive alternative to metals because of their high specific strength or stiffness or their excellent fatigue behaviour. But these superior characteristics can be achieved by using long and continuous fiber composites. If we want to apply these FRP composites on the bend or complicated structures such as gears, we must reinforce the teeth root corner, where the stress level become maximum as shown in Fig. 1. As the long and continuous fiber reinforcement will be difficult for the application on these bend or complicated shape structures, we sometimes perform the machining on the roughly moulded long fiber FRP composites, or use the injection moulded short fiber (chopped strand) FRP. But in the former case this machining must cut the long fiber which was placed along with the stress flow and decrease the strength of structures, and in the later case these superior characteristics will be disappeared. If we want to apply these long fiber FRP composites on more complicated shape parts we must developed new manufacturing process to place the long fiber along with the stress flow.

Fig. 1 Stress concentration at the teeth root

Development of New Manufacturing Process for Long Fiber FRP on Bend or Complicated Structures

In this process we perform the fiber cutting just after continuous fiber placement process and just at the low stress area, which make easy moulding without fail the strength. In Fig. 2 the scemtical view of fiber cut moulding process applied on FRP gear.

Fig. 2 Scemtical view of fiber cut moulding process applied on FRP gear

Strength Evaluation of Bend or Complicated structures wit Long Fiber FRP Composites

A well known weak point of unidirectional fiber FRP composite with bend or complicated shapes is a interlaminar delamination. To clarify the strength criteria of fiber failure or interlaminar delamination failure just at these bend shape corner, the fatigue test specimen is developed as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 Fatigue specimen and failure model

Conclusions

1. Using the developed fiber cut moulding process we can manufacture the carbon fiber FRP gears as shown in Fig. 4.
2. The strength criterion of the FRP composites with bend or complicated structures are obtained using bend specimens.

Fig. 4 Moulded FRP gear

Reference

1. Development of design systems for FRP gears, Proc. Of 10th Int. Conf. On Machine Design and Production (UMTIE2002), (2002) pp. 59